

Influence of rice tungro virus (RTV) infection on severity of bacterial blight (BB) and bacterial leaf streak (BLS) in rice

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Ricefields often are subjected to multiple infection, with the intensity of one disease influenced by other diseases. We studied the influence of RTV infection on severity of BB and BLS diseases in the glasshouse. Susceptible rice cultivar

Disease severity of BB and BLS on TN1 rice plants inoculated with RTV, Cuttack, India.

Inoculation type	Inoculation schedule ^a			Disease severity ^b (%)	
	1st inoculation	Time lapse	2d inoculation	BB	BLS
Same time	RTV	0	XCO/XCOZ	-15	+70
Sequentially	RTV	24	XCO/XCOZ	-25	+115
Sequentially	XCO/XCOZ	24	RTV	-5	+115

^a RTV = rice tungro virus, XCO = *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae*, XCOZ = *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzicola* ^b Estimates based on lesion length of 3 different leaves each from 20 plants. + = increased, - = decreased disease severity on doubly inoculated plants.

TN1 plants (30-d-old, 3- to 4-leaf stage) were artificially inoculated with each incitant alone or in combination.

Disease reaction 7 d after inoculation indicated that BB severity was less in

plants also inoculated with RTV, regardless of inoculation sequence (see table). BLS severity was higher in plants also inoculated with RTV, regardless of inoculation sequence. □

Inducing resistance to rice bacterial blight (BB) by inoculating nonpathogenic isolate of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae*

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We obtained an isolate of *X. campestris* pv. *oryzae*, the incitant of rice BB, which became nonpathogenic across repeated subculturing. We tested the ability of this nonpathogenic isolate to induce resistance to a virulent isolate in the greenhouse, using rice cultivar IR20 (Table 1).

The nonpathogenic isolate was clip-inoculated (10^8 CFU/ml) at the boot leaf stage. The virulent isolate was clip-

Table 2. Efficacy of an avirulent isolate in controlling rice BB. Aduthurai, India.

Sequence of inoculation with virulent and avirulent isolates	Leaf area affected (%)		Disease intensity	
	Trial I	Trial II	Trial I	Trial II
Avirulent + 3 d virulent	2.8	5.0	1.7	3.0
Avirulent + 2 d virulent	5.0	8.0	3.0	3.3
Avirulent + 1 d virulent	4.8	12.0	2.9	3.7
Avirulent - virulent	1.8	2.5	1.3	1.6
Virulent + 1 d avirulent	50.0	70.0	7.0	7.8
Virulent + 2 d avirulent	82.5	75.0	8.3	8.0
Virulent + 3 d avirulent	95.0	80.0	8.8	8.2
Virulent isolate alone (check)	95.0	95.0	8.8	8.8
LSD (P = 0.05)	-	-	0.5	0.6

inoculated (10^8 CFU/ml) 1, 2, and 3 d later. The nonpathogenic and virulent isolates (10^8 CFU/ml each) were mixed and inoculated in one treatment.

In a second experiment, the virulent isolate was inoculated first, followed 1, 2, and 3 d later by inoculation with the nonpathogenic isolate. Disease intensity

was assessed 20 d after inoculation.

The experiments were repeated twice with three replications each.

The nonpathogenic isolate induced resistance to the virulent isolate only when it was inoculated before or simultaneously with the virulent isolate (Table 2). □

Table 1. Effect of differing concentrations of avirulent bacteria on control of rice BB. Aduthurai, India.

Avirulent bacteria (CFU/ml)	Disease intensity ^a
10^8	1.3
10^6	2.3
10^4	3.7
10^2	4.5
0	7.6
LSD (P = 0.05)	0.9

^aStandard evaluation system for rice.

Rice diseases in the Southern Guinea Savannah Zone of Niger State, Nigeria

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Wetland rice in the Southern Guinea Savannah Zone of Niger State of Nigeria is grown in the floodplains

(locally called Fadama). Diseases and pests have become a great menace. We have little information on rice pathogens other than blast (Bl) caused by *Pyricularia oryzae* Cav. Shifts in the status of existing diseases and/or occurrence of new ones are possible.

Experimental rice plots at NCRI, Badeggi, and in farmers' fields at Badeggi, Wuya, Edozhigii, Doko,

Agai, Lapai, Kasha, Mokwa, and Pateggi were surveyed (523 fields). Ricefields were examined at 9 spots (the four corners, midway along each edge, and at the center).

During 1985-87 cropping seasons, BI occurred most frequently. It affected rice at all stages of development and was most severe on late-planted seedlings.

Other fungi diseases observed, in order of prevalence, were brown spot [caused by *Helminthosporium oryzae* Breda de Haan]; leaf scald [*Gerlachia oryzae* Has. and Yokogi]; glume discoloration (many pathogens); sheath blight [*Rhizoctonia solani* Kuhn]; stem rot [*Sclerotium oryzae* Catt]; sheath rot

[*Sarocladium oryzae*]; bakanae [*Gibberella fujikuroi* (Sawada), Ito]; false smut [*Ustilagoidea virens* (Cke) Tak]; and narrow brown leaf spot [*Cercospora oryzae* Miyake].

Rice yellow mottle virus and unconfirmed bacterial blight symptoms were found occasionally. □

Insect management

Incidence of rice stem borer (SB) in the Punjab

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We surveyed incidence of rice SB *Scirpophaga* spp. and *Sesamia* spp. in the Punjab. Samples of rice stubble were collected at harvest from 98 locations in 1986 and from 60 locations in 1987 and dissected to determine tiller infestation and larvae/hill.

Overall tiller infestation was 25% in 1986 and 18% in 1987 (see figure). Traditional rice-growing Kalar tract and Ahmad Nagar were badly infested; Gujarat, Mandi Bahauddin, and Sheikhupura were comparatively less infested.

SBs found were yellow rice SB *Scirpophaga incertulas* (Wlk.), white SB

Incidence of rice SB in the Punjab, 1986-87.

S. innotata (Wlk.), and the pink graminaceous SBs *Sesamia inferens* (Wlk.) and *S. uniformis* (Dudg.).

Scirpophaga spp. made up 357 of 362 larvae collected in 1986, and 1,291 of 1,296 larvae collected in 1987. □

Whitefly (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) - a potential pest of rice in West Africa

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Whiteflies are pests of many crops and also vectors of several plant virus diseases. Whiteflies on rice were first reported in 1966, when *Aleurocybotus indicus* D. and S. was identified in Satara, India. In 1970, *Bemisia tabaci*

M. and H. was found on rice in Madras, India.

A. indicus was reported to be restricted to India, with its preferred hosts graminaceous grasses *Chloris barbata* and *Dactyloctenium aegyptium*. But *A. indicus* was reported in Africa in April 1977, on irrigated rice at Richard Toll, Senegal. In recent years, it has spread to Mauritania, Senegal, Burkina Faso, Nigeria, and Niger.

The insect attacks rice plants from seedling to flowering stages. During the hot, dry season, especially in Feb, Mar,

and Apr, the insect is seen in irrigated rice at the IITA experimental farm at Ibadan. It has become a serious problem in screenhouses and insect rearing cages. When infestation is high, black sooty mold that develops on rice leaves can cause withering and plant death.

In the course of screening for *Diopsis longicornis* in the screenhouse, we found no *Oryza sativa* or *O. glaberrima* varieties that were tolerant of whitefly (500 entries tested).

A calcid larval parasite, *Encarsia* sp. found at Ibadan is definitely not